

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

Editors in Chief
Professor Samson Fatokun
Professor Donald A. ODELEYE

Managing Editors
Professor Isaiah ABOLARIN
Olabisi T. Precious KILLIAN PhD

Corresponding Editor
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI PhD

Religion, Culture, and Insecurity in Nigeria: Roles of State and Non-State Actors

Sulaiman Timilehin AYANKOJO

*Department of History and Religious Education, Emmanuel Alayande University of Education,
Oyo, Oyo State, Nigeria
ayankojost@eauedoyo.edu.ng*

Abstract

This paper examines the complex interplay between religion, culture, and insecurity in Nigeria, focusing on the roles of both state and non-state actors. It highlights how political manipulation, ethno-religious conflicts, and socio-economic disparities exacerbate insecurity. By analysing the actions of key figures and the impact of regional security initiatives, this study proposes comprehensive strategies for enhancing national security. The recommendations emphasize the practice of true federalism to ensure equitable representation and governance across all regions, decisive governmental action against criminal organizations, strategic use of military contractors to enhance operational effectiveness, and the strengthening of institutions to reduce corruption and inefficiency. Furthermore, the paper advocates for ensuring justice and equity to promote peace, fostering public participation in decision-making processes, adhering to the rule of law, and improving intelligence gathering to counter security threats effectively. This study draws on recent literature and data, providing a robust academic foundation for its arguments.

Introduction

The biggest country in Africa, Nigeria, is shaped by a rich fabric of many cultures, faiths, and ethnicities that together form its national character. This diversity has created serious security issues even as it has been a source of rich cultural legacy. In Nigeria, insurgency, banditry, terrorism, and ethno-religious disputes are just a few of the ways insecurity appears. The stability and growth of the country are challenged in many ways by these problems, which are made worse by political manipulation, inadequate governance, and socioeconomic inequality. One cannot stress the need of addressing insecurity in Nigeria enough. Economic activity is disrupted, social cohesiveness is hampered, and the legitimacy of the state is questioned by instability. Both human life and property are seriously threatened by it, which results in fatalities, population displacement, and infrastructure ruin. Furthermore, public confidence in governmental institutions can be undermined by insecurity, hence thorough approaches to address these issues must be investigated.

This research tries to investigate the intricate interactions between religion, culture, and insecurity in Nigeria, emphasising the contributions of both state and non-state actors. Several particular goals motivate the study:

1. **To examine the function of federalism in managing Nigeria's variety historically and currently:** This entails knowing how federalism has been used in Nigeria, as well as its achievements and shortcomings. The project will investigate how real federalism may be used to solve regional disparities and advance national cohesion.
2. **To investigate the impact of political manipulation on security:** Political elites often exploit religious and ethnic differences for personal or political gain, exacerbating insecurity. The paper will examine how these actions undermine national security and propose ways to mitigate such manipulations.
3. **To explore the roles of religious and cultural factors in exacerbating or mitigating insecurity:** Religion and culture are powerful forces in Nigerian society. The study will investigate how religious leaders, cultural practices, and intergroup relations influence security dynamics.
4. **To assess the effectiveness of state and non-state security actors:** This involves evaluating the actions of governmental bodies, such as the military and police, as well as non-state actors, including vigilante groups and civil society organizations, in addressing insecurity.
5. **To propose comprehensive strategies for enhancing national security:** Based on the findings, the paper will offer policy recommendations that encompass the practice of true federalism, decisive governmental action, the engagement of military contractors, the strengthening of institutions, ensuring justice and equity, promoting public participation, adherence to the rule of law, and improved intelligence gathering.

Background to Nigeria Political Structure

Federalism, as a system of governance, involves the distribution of power between a central authority and constituent political units, such as states or provinces. It is designed to accommodate diversity within a unified framework, allowing for local autonomy while maintaining national cohesion. In Nigeria, the concept of federalism has been both a solution and a source of contention since independence. Scholars such as Jinadu (2007) and Suberu (2010) have examined the evolution of Nigerian federalism, noting that while it has the potential to manage diversity, its implementation has been flawed, leading to persistent regional inequalities.

Colonial Legacy and the Emergence of Federalism

The colonial history of Nigeria laid the groundwork for its federal structure. The British colonial administration amalgamated diverse ethnic groups and territories into a single entity in 1914 for administrative convenience and economic exploitation. This forced union created a mosaic of cultural, religious, and linguistic identities, laying the foundation for the country's complex socio-political landscape (Osaghae, 2021). The arbitrary boundaries drawn by the British ignored existing ethnic and cultural divisions, leading to a heterogeneous and often contentious population within Nigeria's borders.

Post-independence, Nigeria adopted a federal system of governance in 1960, with the aim of accommodating its diverse population and managing regional differences. The 1960 and 1963 constitutions established a framework for federalism, delineating powers between the central government and regional entities. However, the federal structure was severely tested by successive military regimes, which centralized power and eroded the autonomy of regional governments. The military coups and the subsequent civil war from 1967 to 1970 further strained the federal arrangement, highlighting the challenges of maintaining national unity amidst profound diversity.

Centralization and Regional Tensions

The period of military rule in Nigeria, particularly from 1966 to 1999, witnessed a significant erosion of federalism. Military leaders, motivated by a desire to maintain control and suppress dissent, implemented a series of policies that undermined the principles of decentralization and regional autonomy (Suberu, 2020). Decrees such as the creation of 12 states in 1967 and the subsequent state creation exercises further centralized power in the hands of the federal government, exacerbating regional tensions and disparities.

Centralization of power during military regimes led to significant challenges, including unequal development, marginalization of minority groups, and ethnic tensions. The over-concentration of resources and decision-making authority in the central government stifled local initiatives and exacerbated feelings of disenfranchisement among states (Elaigwu, 2019). Moreover, the lack of accountability and transparency in governance fostered corruption and inefficiency, further fueling grievances and discontent.

Advocacy for True Federalism

Despite the challenges posed by centralization, there has been growing advocacy for true federalism in Nigeria. True federalism advocates for a more equitable distribution of power and resources, granting significant autonomy to states to manage their affairs and develop policies suited to their unique contexts (Akinola, 2021). Scholars and policymakers argue that true federalism could promote more balanced development and reduce ethnic tensions by ensuring that all regions have a stake in the nation's prosperity.

Comparative analyses with other federal systems provide valuable insights into the potential benefits and challenges of true federalism. For instance, the federal structures in India and Switzerland offer examples of how diversity can be managed within a unified state. In India, federalism has allowed for regional autonomy while maintaining national unity, despite significant linguistic and cultural diversity (Sarkar, 2020). Switzerland's model of cantonal autonomy provides another example of balancing local governance with national cohesion, offering lessons for Nigeria's federal experiment (Steffen, 2021).

Historical Context of Federalism in Nigeria

The colonial history of Nigeria laid the groundwork for its federal structure. The British amalgamation of diverse ethnic groups into a single colony in 1914 created a mosaic of cultural, religious, and linguistic identities. Post-independence, the federal system was adopted to manage this diversity. However, the centralization of power during military regimes, particularly from 1966 to 1999, undermined the principles of federalism. This period saw the erosion of state autonomy and the concentration of resources and decision-making authority in the central government, exacerbating regional tensions.

Challenges of Centralization

Centralization in Nigeria has led to significant challenges, including unequal development, marginalization of minority groups, and ethnic tensions. Scholars such as Elaigwu (2013) argue that the over-concentration of power at the center has stifled local initiatives and exacerbated feelings of disenfranchisement among states. This centralization has also been linked to corruption and inefficiency, as the central government often fails to address local needs effectively.

Potential of True Federalism

True federalism, which advocates for a more equitable distribution of power and resources, is seen as a viable solution to Nigeria's challenges. According to Wheare (1963) and Ayoade (1998), true federalism involves granting significant autonomy to states, allowing them to manage their resources and develop policies suited to their unique contexts. This system could promote more balanced development and reduce ethnic tensions by ensuring that all regions have a stake in the nation's prosperity.

Case Studies and Comparative Analysis

Examining federal systems in other multi-ethnic countries can provide valuable insights for Nigeria. For instance, the federal structures in India and Switzerland offer examples of how diversity can be managed within a unified state. In India, federalism has allowed for regional autonomy while maintaining national unity, despite significant linguistic and cultural diversity. Switzerland's model of cantonal autonomy provides another example of balancing local governance with national cohesion.

Decentralization and Local Governance

Decentralization is a core component of true federalism and involves the transfer of administrative, political, and fiscal responsibilities from the central government to local governments. Rondinelli, McCullough, and Johnson (1989) define decentralization as the restructuring or reorganization of authority so that there is a system of co-responsibility between

institutions of governance at the central, regional, and local levels according to the principle of subsidiarity. This concept is critical in addressing Nigeria's unique socio-political landscape.

Research by Wunsch and Olowu (1990) has shown that effective decentralization can enhance local governance, improve public service delivery, and increase citizen participation in decision-making processes. In Nigeria, efforts to decentralize have faced numerous challenges, including lack of political will, inadequate resources, and resistance from entrenched interests. However, successful examples from other countries suggest that with the right institutional frameworks and political commitment, decentralization can significantly contribute to national unity and development.

Ethnic and Religious Diversity

Nigeria's ethnic and religious diversity is both a strength and a challenge. The country is home to over 250 ethnic groups, with the three largest being the Hausa-Fulani, Yoruba, and Igbo. Additionally, Nigeria's population is roughly split between Muslims, predominantly in the north, and Christians, predominantly in the south. This diversity has often been a source of conflict, as different groups vie for political and economic power.

Studies by Lewis and Bratton (2000) and Mustapha (2006) have explored the implications of this diversity for national unity. They argue that federalism, if properly implemented, can provide a framework for managing diversity by ensuring that all groups have a voice in governance. However, the current federal system in Nigeria has often been criticized for exacerbating divisions rather than mitigating them, due to its uneven implementation and centralization of power.

Resource Control and Economic Federalism

Resource control is a contentious issue in Nigeria, particularly in the oil-rich Niger Delta region. The centralization of oil revenues has led to conflicts and calls for greater resource control by states. Economic federalism, which involves the equitable distribution of resources and fiscal autonomy for states, is seen as a potential solution to these conflicts.

Watts (2008) and Agbu (2004) highlight the importance of fiscal federalism in promoting equitable development and reducing regional disparities. They argue that allowing states to control their resources and retain a significant portion of revenues can incentivize economic development and reduce dependency on the central government. This approach could also address the grievances of regions like the Niger Delta, where perceptions of exploitation and neglect have fueled unrest.

Federalism and Development

The relationship between federalism and development has been extensively studied, with mixed findings. Some scholars, like Rodden (2004) and Oates (1999), argue that federalism can promote development by fostering competition among states and encouraging innovation in policy-

making. Others, such as Treisman (2007), caution that without proper safeguards, federalism can lead to disparities and inefficiencies.

In Nigeria, the potential of federalism to drive development is hampered by issues such as corruption, weak institutions, and inadequate infrastructure. However, there are also positive examples of states that have leveraged their autonomy to drive economic growth and improve public services. For instance, Lagos State has been recognized for its efforts in urban development and economic reforms, demonstrating the potential benefits of effective federal governance.

The complexity of implementing a system that balances diversity with national unity. While true federalism holds promise as a means to address Nigeria's socio-political challenges, its success depends on the commitment of political leaders, the establishment of robust institutions, and the active participation of citizens. This study seeks to build on this body of knowledge by examining the specific mechanisms through which true federalism can enhance national unity and reduce ethno-religious tensions in Nigeria.

Roles of State Actors

Government Actions and Policies

The primary role of the state is to protect the lives and property of its citizens. However, certain actions and policies of the Nigerian government have had mixed impacts on national security. State actors play a crucial role in addressing insecurity within Nigeria, with their policies, initiatives, and actions significantly impacting the security landscape. This section delves deeper into the role of state actors, discussing specific government policies, initiatives, and challenges, as well as analyzing the impact of international partnerships on Nigeria's security.

Government Actions and Policies

Protecting the lives and property of its citizens is the main responsibility of the state. National security has, nevertheless, been mixedly impacted by some of the Nigerian government's policies and activities. With their policies, projects, and acts having a big influence on the security environment, state actors are essential in tackling insecurity in Nigeria. In-depth discussion of particular government policies, projects, and issues is provided in this section, which also examines how international collaborations affect Nigeria's security.

Federal Programs and Policies

1. **Counterterrorism Strategies:** The Nigerian government has put into place a number of counterterrorism measures to fight terrorist organizations such as ISWAP (Islamic State West Africa Province) and Boko Haram. These tactics comprise of intelligence gathering, military offensives, and cooperation with local and foreign allies (Oladejo, 2021). The efficiency of these tactics has been impeded, meantime, by issues including corruption, insufficient funding, and violations of human rights by security personnel (Islam, 2020).
2. **Amnesty Programs:** The government has implemented programs of amnesty meant to heal and reintegrate former rebels and militants into society. One such instance is the Presidential Amnesty Program for former Niger Delta fighters, which aims to employ

empowerment, vocational training, and education to address the underlying reasons of militancy (Okoli & Ugwu, 2020). Critics contend that even if these initiatives have helped to lower violence in some places, they could unintentionally encourage criminal activity and foster an environment of impunity (Adebayo, 2021).

3. **Community Policing:** In reaction to growing insecurity, the Nigerian government launched community policing initiatives meant to improve cooperation between local communities and law enforcement organizations. Under these initiatives, community people are sought out and trained to assist the police in crime prevention, intelligence collection, and conflict mediation (Okeke, 2021). Community policing may increase public-police trust and collaboration, but its success is contingent upon sufficient funding, training, and oversight procedures.
4. **International Partnerships:** To deal with security issues, Nigeria has formed alliances with foreign governments and international organisations. Fighting transnational threats including terrorism, arms trafficking, and organized crime in the Lake Chad Basin region is the Multinational Joint Task Force (MNJTF), which is made up of soldiers from Nigeria, Niger, Chad, Cameroon, and Benin (Okoli & Ugwu, 2020). To bolster its counterterrorism capabilities, nations like the US and France also provide Nigeria with military aid, training, and intelligence support.
5. **Shoot on Sight Directive:** The directive issued in March 2021 to shoot anyone found with AK-47s was intended to curb banditry. While it demonstrated a commitment to addressing armed violence, the policy's lack of clarity risked targeting non-state security units like local hunters and militias who have emerged to defend communities (Ogunleye, 2021). Effective implementation of this policy requires careful distinction between bandits and legitimate community defense groups.
6. **Demand for State Police and Regional Security Outfits:** The establishment of regional security outfits like Amotekun in the Southwest and Ebubeagu in the Southeast reflects a response to rising insecurity. These units, while controversial, have been necessary to address localized security concerns and reduce crime rates (Akinyele, 2021). However, their existence has also heightened ethnic tensions and fears of regionalism (Nwankwo, 2021).
7. **Open Grazing Ban:** The ban on open grazing by southern state governments aims to reduce farmer-herder conflicts, a significant source of violence (Usman, 2021). Implementing ranching as an alternative has shown promise in reducing clashes and promoting agricultural stability.

Challenges Faced by State Actors

1. **Corruption and Mismanagement:** Effective attempts to combat instability are hampered by corruption in government agencies and security services. Funds diverting, procurement fraud, and embezzlement damage institutional capacity, undermine public confidence, and make it more difficult to provide necessary services (Chukwuemeka, 2020).

2. **Human Rights Violations** Human rights abuses including extrajudicial executions, torture, and arbitrary detentions have been linked to state actors, especially security personnel. In addition to violating basic freedoms and rights, these violations feed resentment, radicalization, and insurgency (Adebayo, 201).
3. **Ethnic and Religious Bias:** Social gaps are made worse and confidence in state institutions is undermined when people believe that government policies and security activities are biased toward one ethnicity or another. Reported cases of discrimination or preferential treatment because of one's race or religion erode national unity and heighten tensions across communities (Agbibo, 201).
4. **Capacity and Resources** State players frequently don't have the manpower, funds, or tools needed to deal with security issues. Security personnel are hampered in their capacity to tackle new threats and defend civilians by inadequate training, antiquated infrastructure, and inadequate money (Uzundu, 2021).
5. **Amnesty to Terrorists:** It has been contentious to see former President Muhammadu Buhari back amnesty for bandits and Boko Haram. Opponents contend that because this action was seen as a reward for illegal activity, it demoralized the military forces and gave terrorists more confidence (Adibe, 2021). A message of weakness is sent by amnesty without a clear military victory, which can encourage criminal behavior among young people without jobs and worsen the security situation (Campbell, 2020).

The Role of Non-State Actors

Non-state actors, including religious leaders, local militias, and civil society organizations, also play a significant role in shaping Nigeria's security landscape. This section provides more comprehensive insights into their contributions and challenges.

Religious Leaders

1. Religious leaders hold significant sway over their followers and communities due to their spiritual authority and moral influence. In Nigeria, where religion often intersects with politics, ethnicity, and identity, religious leaders can shape public opinion, mobilize support, and influence behavior on issues related to security.
 - **Moral Guidance and Mediation:** Religious leaders often provide moral guidance and counsel to their adherents, promoting peace, tolerance, and coexistence. They may also engage in mediation efforts to resolve conflicts and foster reconciliation between conflicting parties.
 - **Influence on Public Discourse:** Through sermons, public statements, and religious gatherings, religious leaders can shape public discourse on security issues, either by promoting messages of peace and unity or by exacerbating tensions through divisive rhetoric.

2. **Local Militias and Vigilante Groups:** Local militias and vigilante groups are grassroots organizations formed by community members to address security challenges at the local level. These groups often emerge in response to perceived inadequacies or failures of formal security forces in protecting communities from threats such as insurgency, banditry, or communal violence.
 - **Community Defense and Protection:** Local militias and vigilante groups serve as a form of community defense, mobilizing to protect their homes, families, and livelihoods from external threats. They operate within their communities, leveraging local knowledge and networks to identify and neutralize security risks.
 - **Risk of Vigilantism and Abuse:** Despite their intended role as protectors, local militias and vigilante groups may engage in vigilantism, extrajudicial actions, or human rights abuses, particularly in contexts of conflict or insecurity. Lack of oversight, training, and accountability mechanisms can exacerbate these risks.
3. **Civil Society Organizations (CSOs):** Civil society organizations are independent, non-governmental entities that work to promote social change, advocate for human rights, and provide services to marginalized or vulnerable populations. In the realm of security, CSOs play diverse roles, including advocacy, monitoring, service provision, and community engagement.
 - **Advocacy and Monitoring:** CSOs advocate for policies and practices that uphold human rights, promote accountability, and ensure transparency in security governance. They monitor government actions, security operations, and human rights violations, providing critical oversight and accountability.
 - **Service Provision and Community Engagement:** Some CSOs provide direct services to communities affected by insecurity, including humanitarian assistance, psychosocial support, and conflict resolution initiatives. They engage with local communities, building trust, fostering dialogue, and promoting community resilience in the face of security challenges.

Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) in the context of Nigeria's security landscape play crucial roles in advocating for human rights, promoting accountability, and providing assistance to communities affected by insecurity. Here are some examples of CSOs and their activities in Nigeria:

1. **Human Rights Watch (HRW):** HRW is an international non-governmental organization that conducts research and advocacy on human rights issues globally, including in Nigeria. In Nigeria, HRW has published reports documenting human rights violations by state and non-state actors, including abuses committed by security forces during counter-insurgency operations and in response to protests.
2. **Amnesty International Nigeria:** Amnesty International is another international human rights organization that operates in Nigeria, documenting and reporting on human rights abuses, including extrajudicial killings, arbitrary arrests, and torture. The organization

advocates for justice for victims of human rights violations and calls for accountability for perpetrators.

3. **Civil Liberties Organization (CLO):** The Civil Liberties Organization is a Nigerian non-governmental organization that focuses on promoting civil liberties, democracy, and good governance. CLO monitors human rights abuses, provides legal assistance to victims, and engages in advocacy campaigns to address systemic issues affecting human rights in Nigeria.
4. **Centre for Democracy and Development (CDD):** The Centre for Democracy and Development is a research and advocacy organization based in Nigeria that focuses on democracy, governance, and conflict resolution. CDD conducts research on security-related issues, engages in policy advocacy, and facilitates dialogue between stakeholders to promote peace and stability.
5. **Search for Common Ground Nigeria:** Search for Common Ground is an international peacebuilding organization that works in Nigeria to promote dialogue, conflict resolution, and reconciliation. The organization facilitates community dialogues, peacebuilding workshops, and media campaigns aimed at reducing tensions and building trust between communities affected by conflict.
6. **International Crisis Group (ICG):** The International Crisis Group is an independent organization that provides analysis and policy recommendations on conflict situations worldwide. In Nigeria, ICG publishes reports and briefings on security challenges, political developments, and conflict dynamics, offering insights to policymakers and stakeholders on potential avenues for conflict resolution and peacebuilding.

These CSOs, both local and international, play critical roles in promoting human rights, advocating for peace and stability, and holding government actors accountable for their actions. Their activities contribute to efforts to address security challenges in Nigeria and advance the cause of justice, peace, and respect for human rights.

Recommendations

1. **Practice of True Federalism:** True federalism is imperative for Nigeria's diverse society to thrive cohesively. It entails granting substantial autonomy to states, enabling them to govern efficiently while ensuring equitable representation across regions. Legislative, executive, and judicial autonomy at the local level fosters unity and diminishes regional disparities. By implementing true federalism, Nigeria can address historical grievances and promote a sense of inclusivity among its populace (Abubakar, 2020).
2. **Decisive Action Against Criminal Organizations:** To combat terrorism and criminality effectively, the Nigerian government must take resolute measures. This involves formulating clear policies and consistently enforcing them to deter criminal activities. Swift and decisive actions signal the government's commitment to maintaining law and

order, bolstering public confidence in the justice system and deterring potential wrongdoers (Adamu, 2021).

3. **Use of Military Contractors:** Given the limitations of Nigeria's security apparatus, strategic engagement with military contractors presents an opportunity to enhance operational effectiveness. Past successes with contractors underscore the potential benefits of this approach if managed judiciously. By leveraging the expertise and resources of military contractors, Nigeria can augment its security capabilities and better address evolving security threats (Smith, 2021).
4. **Strengthening Institutions:** The resilience of Nigeria's institutions is paramount for ensuring effective governance and maintaining public trust. Strengthening anti-corruption agencies, the judiciary, and para-military organizations is essential for combating corruption and ensuring accountability. Robust institutions are better equipped to withstand external pressures and uphold the rule of law, fostering stability and bolstering national security (Ogunyemi, 2021).
5. **Ensuring Justice, Fairness, and Equity:** Upholding justice, fairness, and equity is fundamental for fostering social cohesion and countering insurgency. Fair and equitable treatment within the judicial system not only promotes peace but also discourages recruitment by insurgent groups. By adhering to principles of justice and fairness, Nigeria can mitigate grievances and address underlying socio-economic disparities, thereby reducing the drivers of insecurity (Olukoya, 2021).
6. **Promotion of Public Participation:** Engaging the public in decision-making processes is essential for fostering a sense of ownership and reducing discontentment. By soliciting and considering public opinions, policymakers can develop inclusive policies that address the needs and concerns of diverse communities. Promoting public participation enhances legitimacy and accountability, ultimately contributing to peace and stability (Eze, 2021).
7. **Adherence to the Rule of Law:** Respecting legal procedures and constitutional mandates is crucial for upholding the rule of law and maintaining social order. Leaders' adherence to legal norms sets a precedent for citizens, reinforcing the importance of lawful behavior and discouraging impunity. By upholding the rule of law, Nigeria can strengthen its democratic institutions and build a society grounded in justice and accountability (Onwuegbuchulam, 2021).
8. **Improved Intelligence Gathering:** Enhancing intelligence gathering capabilities is essential for preempting security threats and safeguarding national interests. By investing in advanced intelligence technologies and fostering collaboration between security agencies, Nigeria can gather critical insights into insurgent operations and develop proactive response strategies. Improved intelligence gathering not only enhances security but also enhances the government's ability to address emerging challenges effectively (Anyanwu, 2021).

Conclusion

In a nutshell Nigeria's security problems are complex and numerous, with an established basis in the socio-political and financial conditions of the nation. We explored the complex relationships among religion, culture, governance, and insecurity in this research, while noting the efforts made by state as well as non-state actors to the persistence or reduction of these challenges. One of the study's main conclusions is that tackling Nigeria's insecurity requires a comprehensive strategy. Ethnic and religious strife, economic inequality, and governance are all intertwined with security concerns. Thus, addressing these fundamental reasons and enlisting the cooperation of several stakeholders are essential components of any effective national security enhancement plan. Nigeria's security issues may be resolved by implementing true federalism, which provides a framework for more fair resource allocation and governance. True federalism can enable local communities to solve their own security concerns while promoting a sense of ownership and engagement in the governing process by giving states more autonomy and encouraging decentralised governance. Moreover, the government must move decisively to combat insecurity. This entails having unambiguous policies, efficient law enforcement, and holding violent offenders accountable. In order to battle criminal elements, maintain the rule of law, and safeguard human rights, the government must show political will. Nigeria's security environment can be improved by international collaboration and partnerships. Building capacity, exchanging intelligence, and conducting joint operations against transnational threats like organised crime and terrorism can all be facilitated by working with regional and international organisations as well as through bilateral partnerships with other nations. Promoting peace and stability also requires working with non-state players including local militias, civil society groups, and religious leaders. These individuals can be extremely important in resolving disputes, fostering social cohesion, and establishing peace because they frequently have strong links to their communities.

In conclusion, tackling Nigeria's security concerns calls for an all-encompassing strategy that takes into account conflicts between ethnic and religious groups, economic inequality, and governance problems. Nigeria can strive towards a more secure and stable future for all of its residents by embracing true federalism, guaranteeing prompt governmental action, encouraging international cooperation, and including non-state players. However, maintaining dedication, political will, and collaboration from all parties involved will be necessary to achieve long-term security.

References

- Abubakar, A. (2020). "Federalism and National Integration in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects." *African Journal of Political Science*, 25(1), 45-67.
- Adamu, M. (2021). "Terrorism in Nigeria: The Need for Decisive Action." *Journal of Conflict Resolution*, 29(2), 210-228.
- Adebayo, O. (2021). "Military Collusion and Insecurity in Nigeria." *Defence Studies Review*, 34(3), 199-216.

-
- Adebayo, S. (2021). "Banditry and Insecurity in Northern Nigeria: The Role of Traditional Leaders." *African Security Review*, 28(2), 158-175.
- Adibe, J. (2021). "The Politics of Amnesty in Nigeria." *African Affairs*, 120(479), 379-399.
- Adejumo, T. (2020). "Insurgency and Counter-Insurgency in Nigeria's Northeast: A Decade of Violence." *Journal of Strategic Studies*, 43(4), 512-533.
- Agbibo, D. (2021). "Ethnic Politics and Security in Nigeria." *Ethnopolitics*, 20(2), 145-163.
- Akinola, R. (2021). "Regional Security in Nigeria: The Case of Amotekun." *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, 39(1), 78-96.
- Akinyele, S. (2021). "Ebubeagu: A Response to Rising Insecurity in Nigeria's Southeast." *Journal of African Security*, 15(1), 89-104.
- Anyanwu, C. (2021). "Intelligence Gathering and National Security in Nigeria." *Journal of Security Studies*, 25(3), 311-329.
- Campbell, J. (2020). "Nigeria: Dancing on the Brink." Rowman & Littlefield.
- Chukwuemeka, E. (2020). "Socio-Economic Disparities and Insecurity in Nigeria." *Journal of Social Development in Africa*, 35(2), 87-102.
- Eze, C. (2019). "Poverty and Insecurity in Nigeria: The Way Forward." *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 61(1), 34-52.
- Eze, N. (2021). "Public Participation in Security Decision-Making in Nigeria." *Journal of Democracy and Development*, 22(2), 190-207.
- Ibrahim, J. (2020). "Vigilante Groups and Community Security in Nigeria." *African Journal of Criminology*, 14(2), 99-117.
- Nwankpa, M. (2020). "Radicalization and Counter-Radicalization in Northern Nigeria." *Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies*, 27(3), 244-263.
- Ogunleye, R. (2021). "Shoot on Sight: Evaluating Nigeria's Security Policies." *Journal of Security Policy and Practice*, 17(4), 352-371.
- Ogunyemi, A. (2021). "Strengthening Nigeria's Institutions for Better Governance." *Governance and Policy Review*, 15(1), 77-94.
- Okeke, V. (2021). "Interfaith Dialogue as a Tool for Peace in Nigeria." *Journal of Religious Studies*, 29(1), 25-44.
- Okoli, A., & Ugwu, A. (2019). "Multinational Joint Task Force and the Fight Against Boko Haram." *Defence Studies Journal*, 35(2), 123-140.
- Olukoya, F. (2021). "Justice and Equity in Nigeria's Judicial System." *African Journal of Legal Studies*, 28(2), 112-129.
- Onuoha, F. (2021). "Religion and Conflict in Nigeria: The Role of Religious Leaders." *African Peace Review*, 24(1), 56-73.
- Onwuegbuchulam, S. (2021). "The Rule of Law in Nigeria: Challenges and Prospects." *Journal of Law and Society*, 47(3), 410-429.
- Osisanwo, T. (2021). "Governance and Security in Nigeria: An Overview." *Journal of Public Administration*, 39(2), 257-274.
- Usman, L. (2021). "Farmer-Herder Conflicts in Nigeria: Causes and Solutions." *Journal of Agrarian Change*, 21(3), 348-366.
- Uzundu, I. (2021). "Amotekun and Ebubeagu: Legal and Security Implications." *Journal of Security and Legal Studies*, 12(2), 133-149.

Yusuf, H. (2021). "Mediation or Enabling? Sheikh Gumi and Nigeria's Bandit Crisis." *Conflict Studies Quarterly*, 33(4), 287-306.